

**Understanding food sustainability from a consumer perspective: a cross cultural
exploration**

P. Torán-Pereg ^{a, b}, M. Mora ^{a, b}, M. Thomsen ^c, Z. Palkova ^d, S. Novoa ^a, L. Vázquez-
Araújo ^{a, b, *}

^a BCCInnovation, Technology Center in Gastronomy, Basque Culinary Center,
Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

^b Basque Culinary Center, Faculty of Gastronomic Sciences, Mondragon Unibertsitatea,
Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

^c Food Chemistry, Department of Food Science, Faculty of Science, University of
Copenhagen, Rolighedsvej 30, 1958 Frederiksberg, Denmark

^d Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Slovakia

Corresponding author: lvazquez@bculinary.com

1 **Abstract**

2 To successfully transition to more sustainable diets, it is necessary to understand
3 consumers' demands and expectations. The present exploratory research shows a cross-
4 cultural study (Spain, Slovakia, Denmark) in which different aspects were included in an
5 online survey: (i) food choice motivations, (ii) the importance that consumers give to
6 different attributes of four product categories: fruit and vegetables, bakery, meat, and fish,
7 and (iii) the concepts that consumers' relate to the term "sustainability". The results
8 showed preliminary significant differences among countries, suggesting that developing
9 strategies and new products to promote sustainable consumption habits must address
10 these cultural differences.

11

12 **KEYWORDS**

13 FOOD CHOICE, FOOD CATEGORIES, FOOD WASTE, ONLINE SURVEY,
14 EUROPEAN REGIONS

INTRODUCTION

15 The food system is considered one of the main drivers of climate change and its activities
16 require an intensive use of resources (Poore & Nemecek, 2018; Shukla et al., 2019). It is
17 estimated that in a business-as-usual scenario, the effects of the food system on the
18 environment could increase by 50-80 % between 2010 and 2050 (Springmann et al.,
19 2018). A change towards more sustainable production and dietary patterns (e.g., an
20 increase in plant-rich diets, healthy calories, high yields and efficiency, food loss and
21 waste reduction) has been reported to significantly reduce the environmental impact of
22 the food system (Frehner et al., 2021; Osei-Owusu et al., 2022), preventing a higher
23 increase of the targeted increment of 1.5 °C – 2 °C in the average global temperature
24 associated to climate change (Clark et al., 2020). However, food preferences, choices,
25 and eating habits are difficult to change, as they are strongly linked with people's
26 lifestyles and their socio-cultural environments (Vermei et al., 2020).

27 Consumers' awareness on sustainability has increased during the last years. A recent
28 study made by the European Consumer Organization (2020) revealed that 42,6% of
29 consumers reported a "sustainability concern" when assessing their own eating habits,
30 but "sustainability" was not defined. The World Commission on Environment and
31 Development published in 1987 a definition to understand sustainability as a balance
32 among environmental, social, and economic dimensions (WCED, 1987); from that
33 moment on, different ideas have been proposed on how to reach this equilibrium because
34 every context has its particular necessities. For that reason, some authors have exposed
35 the need to understand how consumers perceive the idea of "sustainable" to succeed in
36 proposing initiatives that seek more viable consumption habits (Simpson & Radford,
37 2012; White et al., 2019). Additionally, insights suggested by consumers from different
38

39 cultures could help promoting a global and sustainable food consumption but focusing on
40 local interests (EAT-Globescan, 2021).

41 Chen & Antonelli (2020) identified some of the factors affecting food choice and
42 classified them into three main categories: (1) Food-related features: intrinsic and
43 extrinsic, (2) individual differences: biological, physical, psychological, cognitive, and
44 social factors, and (3) society-related features. In the last years, food companies have been
45 trying to adapt or design foods to meet consumer needs and preferences, favoring the
46 selection of their products, and optimizing their processes to reduce the environmental
47 impact of their activities. The consumer has been placed at the center of the reformulation
48 or design process, and several methods have been designed to drive the process and
49 collect consumers' inputs (Busse & Siebert, 2017; Dijksterhuis, 2016).

50 Pucci et al. (2021) showed that different personal attitudes such as the openness to new
51 foods, the involvement in food trends, or the use of social media, could have a different
52 impact on the adoption of a sustainable diet in different countries (Italy, Poland, Germany,
53 USA, Brazil, Japan, Korea and China). With the aim of increasing understanding on
54 consumers' ideas about sustainability linked to food products, and how to properly
55 communicate food properties to encourage sustainable decisions related to food habits,
56 this study was designed to (i) identify the main food consumption motivations, (ii)
57 identify which attributes related to the concept of sustainability were considered
58 important in different product categories, and (iii) understand the perception of the
59 concept "sustainability" using an online survey disseminated in 3 European regions which
60 represent different European gastronomies (Spain -Mediterranean-, Slovakia -central
61 Europe-, Denmark -North Europe-).

62

63

MATERIALS AND METHODS

64 An online questionnaire was designed and disseminated using the RedJade® sensory
65 software (RedJade Sensory Solutions, LLC; CA, USA). Over 450 adult respondents were
66 reached using the communication channels of the different organizations participating in
67 the research (62 % women, 37 % men, 1 % preferred not to disclose; 5 % from the 18-25
68 years old group, 36 % from the 26-35 y/o group, 26 % from the 36-45 y/o group, 18 %
69 from the 46-55 y/o group, and 15 % over 56 y/o), and a set of responses was collected
70 from citizens in Spain, Slovakia, and Denmark. From the collected answers, after filtering
71 incomplete questionnaires, 137 responses were used from each country for the data
72 analyses. The first section of the questionnaire was composed by the single-item Food
73 Choice Questionnaire reported by Onwezen et al. (2019), in which the relevance of 11
74 different dimensions related to food choice motivations have to be rated using a 7-points
75 scale (“1 = completely disagree”, “4 = neither agree, nor disagree”, and “7 = completely
76 agree”). Then, a Check-All-That-Apply (CATA) question was presented, showing 47
77 terms to be related to the “sustainability” concept; the list of terms was based on the one
78 reported by Simpson & Radford (2012) with slight modifications. Finally, to identify
79 which attributes consumers report as impactful to select different food categories (fruits
80 and vegetables, bakery products, meat, and fish), four CATA questions were included
81 (one for each category); the list of attributes was based on the one reported by Verain et
82 al. (2017), and the questions were introduced with the sentence “it is important to me that
83 *category* products are ...”. The entire survey was designed in English, reviewed by
84 researchers of the 3 participant countries, and back-translated to Danish, Slovak, and
85 Spanish languages.

86 Responses to the single-item FCQ were analyzed using a two-ways Analysis of Variance
87 (ANOVA) using “motivation” and “country” as factors, and the interaction
88

89 motivation*country. The responses to the CATA questions were analyzed using a
90 Cochran's Q pairwise comparisons test based on the McNemar-Bonferroni approach to
91 identify significant differences among countries. All the results were analyzed using
92 XLSTAT 2009.6.03 (Addinsoft, USA).

93

94 **RESULTS**

95 Significant differences were found in the Food Choice responses for both "motivations"
96 and "country" factors, as well as for the interaction "motivation*country". The three
97 explored European countries presented different Food Choice profiles, as shown in Figure
98 1. Significant differences were detected for 7 of the 11 considered attributes among
99 countries ($p < 0.05$). All countries considered the hedonic aspect of foods important, being
100 "provides me with pleasure sensations" one of the motives with higher ratings. Besides
101 this one, "natural", "healthy" and "affordable", were the most important motives in
102 Denmark, and "healthy", "natural", and "environmentally friendly" were the most
103 important in Slovakia and Spain. Responses from Slovakia highlighted because of the
104 high ratings on the "familiar", and "animal-friendly" aspects of food choice motivations.
105 Previous investigations have detected that one of the main barriers for consumers when
106 selecting a food product was the need to choose between hedonic and low-impact options
107 (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2019), and therefore the eco-design of a food product needs to
108 also focus in tastiness to be successful. Although there is still a need to fill the gap between
109 intentions and action, acceptance of different food products could be boosted by
110 highlighting the attributes of interests reported by the population of the targeted country
111 (Loy et al., 2016).

112 Table 1 shows the CATA results, indicating the concepts that were marked by
113 respondents when asked about "sustainability". Significant differences across countries

114 were found in 13 of the 17 items. Spain was the country that showed a wider vision on
115 the meaning of “sustainability”, with over 50 % respondents marking 17 terms which
116 included the environmental (e.g., "environmentally friendly", "minimize waste"), social
117 (e.g., "work ethics", "health"), economic (e.g., "economic balance") and time (e.g.,
118 “future generations”, “future”) dimensions. Over 50 % of Slovakian respondents marked
119 eight concepts, which coincided with some of the ones marked by Spanish respondents
120 and that comprised environmental and time dimensions. In the case of Denmark, only
121 four terms were mentioned by over 50 % of respondents, all of them associated with the
122 environmental dimension.

123 Figure 2 shows the mentioned frequency of the attributes that respondents considered
124 important in different product categories. In the case of Fruits and Vegetables, “healthy”,
125 “have a low usage of pesticides”, and “tasty” were the main concerns for consumers from
126 the three countries (over 50 % of respondents marked those terms). However, significant
127 differences ($p < 0.05$) were found among countries for 13 of the 15 presented terms.
128 Slovakia highlighted because of a higher % of respondents selecting “healthy” and “come
129 from my country”. In general, Spanish and Slovakian respondents selected more
130 attributes than Danish respondents did, including “seasonal”, “produces little waste”,
131 “have no packaging”, “comes from my region”, “locally produced”, and “short
132 transportation distance”. A higher % of Danish consumers marked the “have an ecolabel”
133 option.

134 For Bakery products, “tasty” was also an important property for the three studied
135 countries. Nevertheless, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were shown among countries
136 in 11 of the 15 presented terms, with a higher % of respondents from Slovakia choosing
137 “gives little waste” and “comes from my country”, and a higher % of Spanish and
138 Slovakian respondents marking “healthy”, “comes from my region”, “locally produced”,

139 and “short transportation”. “Having an ecolabel” was marked by a higher % of Danish
140 and Slovakian respondents than Spanish ones.

141 Significant differences were found ($p < 0.05$) in 11 of the 16 presented terms related to
142 Meat products. Slovakia had a larger % of respondents marking “comes from my
143 country”. Spain and Slovakia showed a similar response pattern in some attributes
144 because over 50 % of consumers marked “environmentally friendly”, “animal welfare
145 certification”, and “locally produced”.

146 In the case of the Fish products, in concordance with the other food categories, the
147 attribute that seemed to be important for more than 50 % of participants of the three
148 countries ($p > 0.05$) was “tasty”. “Healthy” was also a highly mentioned attribute in
149 Slovakia and Spain, as well as “environmentally friendly”, “produces little waste”, “have
150 a short transportation distance” and “have a low carbon footprint”. In addition, while for
151 the Spanish participants, “are caught in a sustainable way” was a highly valued attribute,
152 “low usage of antibiotics” was important for the Slovak respondents.

153 Findings of the present exploratory research could be summarized highlighting the
154 differences among countries in terms of food choice motivations and perception of
155 sustainable-linked concepts, as well as observing the reasons for choosing specific foods
156 from different categories in the studied countries. Spanish, Danish, and Slovakian
157 respondents showed different ways of understanding the link between food and
158 sustainability, although have a common European regulations framework. Results shown
159 in the present study could be used as a baseline to start researching the role of consumers’
160 perception and their habits on moving forward a sustainable system. Using different
161 labels adapted to consumers’ understanding and interests, designing guidelines and
162 communication campaigns in which the key communication drivers of each food category
163 are observed, including educational tips related to sustainable food choices at school and

164 university programs may be examples on how to reach different citizen segments, always
165 trying to address consumers' misconceptions to promote more sustainable habits (e.g.:
166 Lazzarini et al., 2018).

167

168 **IMPLICATIONS FOR GASTRONOMY**

168

169 The present manuscript includes a cross-cultural study of 3 European regions on
170 consumers' motivations for choosing general foods, and specific product categories in
171 particular. In addition, the results offer an overview of the different ideas that the concept
172 of "sustainability" arouses in consumers. Although it is a simple exploratory study,
173 findings are relevant to help food developers and the entire HORECA sector drive a more
174 sustainable food system by providing data to better understand consumers and diners of
175 different countries. In a world increasingly concerned about climate change and the
176 environmental impact of certain human activities, the information on how to drive
177 consumer choices to a more sustainable option is essential to promote a successful
178 change.

178

179

180 **CONCLUSIONS**

181 Results of the present exploratory research suggested that any food product belonging to
182 different categories needs to be "tasty" to be selected by consumers, and therefore
183 successful in the market. "Sustainability" cannot be disaggregated from "deliciousness"
184 because consumers from the three researched countries highly valued "pleasure
185 sensations" in the Food Choice Questionnaire, and "tastiness" of the different food
186 categories. The responses about the ideas associated with "sustainability" revealed some
187 common thoughts of the three countries: those that are particularly related to the
188 environmental dimension. Therefore, different strategies should be developed depending

189 on the culture to highlight or reinforce the importance of the different dimensions of
190 sustainability to drive the path to a more sustainable consumption. Although preliminary
191 and considered tentative because of the limited participation in each country, the present
192 results could be considered a starting point to deep into the citizens understanding of
193 sustainable food related practices, as well as cultural differences that may impact habits
194 and food choices.

195

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND FUNDING

196

197 The present research was included in the FOODRUS project, which has received funding
198 from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
199 grant agreement N°101000617.

200

201

REFERENCES

202

203 Aschemann-Witzel, J., Ares, G., Thøgersen, J., Monteleone, E., 2019. A sense of
204 sustainability? – How sensory consumer science can contribute to sustainable
205 development of the food sector. *Trends Food Sci.Tech.* 90, 180–186.
206 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2019.02.021>

207

208 Busse, M., Siebert, R., 2017. The role of consumers in food innovation processes. *Europ.*
209 *J. Innov.* 21, 20–43. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-03-2017-0023>

210

211 Chen, P.J., Antonelli, M., 2020. Conceptual models of food choice: influential factors
212 related to foods, individual differences, and society. *Foods.* 9(12), 1–21.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9121898>

213

214 Clark, M.A., Domingo, N.G.G., Colgan, K., Thakrar, S.K., Tilman, D., Lynch, J.,
215 Azevedo, I.L., Hill, J. D., 2020. Global food system emissions could preclude
216

217

213 achieving the 1.5° and 2°C climate change targets. *Science*. 370(6517), 705–708.
214 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba7357>

215 Dijksterhuis, G., 2016. New product failure: Five potential sources discussed. *Trends*
216 *FoodSci. Technol.* 50, 243–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2016.01.016>

217 Frehner, A., De Boer, I.J.M., Muller, A., Van Zanten, H.H.E., Schader, C., 2022.
218 Consumer strategies towards a more sustainable food system: insights from
219 Switzerland. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 115(4), 1039–1047.
220 <https://doi.org/10.1093/AJCN/NQAB401>

221 Lazzarini, G. A., Visschers, V. H., Siegrist, M., 2018. How to improve consumers'
222 environmental sustainability judgements of foods. *J. Clean. Prod.* 198, 564-574.
223 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.033>

224 Loy, L. S., Wieber, F., Gollwitzer, P. M., Oettingen, G., 2016. Supporting sustainable
225 food consumption: Mental contrasting with implementation intentions (MCII)
226 aligns intentions and behavior. *Front. Psychol.* 7, 607.
227 <https://doi.org/10.3389/FPSYG.2016.00607/BIBTEX>

228 Onwezen, M. C., Reinders, M. J., Verain, M. C. D., Snoek, H. M., 2019. The development
229 of a single-item Food Choice Questionnaire. *Food Qual. Pref.* 71, 34–45.
230 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2018.05.005>

231 Osei-Owusu, A.K., Towa, E., Thomsen, M., 2022. Exploring the pathways towards the
232 mitigation of the environmental impact of food consumption. *Sci. Total Environ.*
233 806(2), 150528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150528>

234 Poore, J., Nemecek, T., 2018. Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers
235 and consumers. *Science*, 360(6392), 987–992.
236 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaq0216>

237 Pucci, T., Casprini, E., Sogari, G., Zanni, L., 2021., Exploring the attitude towards the
238 adoption of a sustainable diet: a cross-country comparison, *Br. Food J.* 124(13),
239 290-304. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-04-2021-0426>

240 Shukla, P.R., Skeg, J., Buendia, E.C., Masson-Delmotte, V., Pörtner, H.O., Roberts, D.
241 C., ... Malley, J., 2019. Climate Change and Land: an IPCC special report on climate
242 change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food
243 security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems.
244 <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/chapter/summary-for-policymakers/>

245 Simpson, B.J.K., Radford, S.K., 2012. Consumer perceptions of sustainability: A free
246 elicitation study. *J. Nonprofit Public Sect. Mark.* 24(4), 272–291.
247 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10495142.2012.733654>

248 Springmann, M., Clark, M., Mason-D’Croz, D., Wiebe, K., Bodirsky, B.L., Lassaletta,
249 L., ... Willett, W., 2018. Options for keeping the food system within environmental
250 limits. *Nature*, 562(7728), 519–525. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41586-018-0594-0>

251 Verain, M. C. D., Sijtsema, S. J., Dagevos, H., Antonides, G., Rosen, M. A., 2017.
252 Attribute segmentation and communication effects on healthy and sustainable
253 consumer diet intentions. *Sustainability*, 9(743). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9050743>

254 White, K., Habib, R., Hardisty, D. J., 2019. How to SHIFT consumer behaviors to be
255 more sustainable: a literature review and guiding framework. *J. Mark.* 83(3), 22-
256 49. <https://doi:10.1177/0022242919825649>.

257 WCED., 1987. Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our
258 Common Future.
259 [https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-](https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf)
260 [future.pdf](https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf)

261

FIGURES AND TABLES

262

263

264 **Table 1.** Relative frequency of mentioning different terms associated with
265 “sustainability” marked by over 50% of respondents in at least one country. Different
266 letters within the same row to indicate significant differences among countries ($p \leq 0.05$;
267 pairwise comparisons using the McNemar-Bonferroni approach).

Concept	Spain	Slovakia	Denmark
Environmentally friendly	0.81 a	0.60 b	0.54 b
Minimizing waste	0.76 a	0.62 ab	0.48 b
Environment	0.76 a	0.62 a	0.51 b
Ecologically friendly	0.75 a	0.45 b	0.45 b
Recycling	0.73	0.58	0.50
Low footprint	0.68 a	0.57 a	0.31 b
Green	0.58	0.44	0.46
Future generations	0.58	0.53	0.36
Personal responsibility	0.58 a	0.53 a	0.32 b
Reduced packaging	0.58	0.48	0.50
Fair trade	0.56 a	0.38 b	0.44 a
Health	0.55 a	0.42 a	0.26 b
Future	0.55 a	0.50 a	0.31 b
Local sources	0.54 a	0.47 a	0.33 b
Workplace ethics (e.g., sweatshop, child labour, ethical labour)	0.53 a	0.38 ab	0.29 b
Balancing money	0.52 a	0.08 b	0.12 b
Managing for the future	0.50 a	0.30 b	0.38 ab

268

269

270

271 **Figure 1.** Two-ways ANOVA results of the Food Choice Questionnaire showing the
 272 interaction “motivations*country”. Legend: Different letters to indicate significant
 273 differences among countries by the Food Choice motivation concept.

274

275

276

277

278

279

280

281

282

283

284

285

286

287 **Figure 2.** Frequency of mention of terms that respondents marked when asked about
 288 important attributes in a) fruit and vegetables, b) bakery, c) meat, and d) fish products.
 289 Legend. Terms marked with (*) were significantly different among countries ($p < 0.05$);
 290 dashed line to highlight the 50% threshold.

291

292